

Deliverable 3.6

Report on Inter-comprehension competence framework

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Co-funded by
the Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Torino 30/06/2021

Technical references

Project Acronym	UNITA
Project Title	UNITA - Universitas Montium
Document Author	Elisa Corino
Project Coordinator	Maurizio De Tullio
Project Duration	36 Months
Deliverable No.	3.6 - Inter-comprehension competence framework
Dissemination level *	PU
Work Package	3
Task	3.2.1
Lead beneficiary	Università degli Studi di Torino
Due date of deliverable	30/06/2021
Actual submission date	30/06/2021
Document version	1.0

* PU = Public; PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services); RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services); CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Agency Services)

Document history:

Version	Date	Created by	Short Description of Changes

Document Location

The latest version of this document is stored in UNITA Datacloud>Documents>Unita_Project_Documents> Unita_Deliverables.

Updating the intercomprehension competence framework

The UNITA competence framework in intercomprehension (IC) is based on three founding documents concerning IC and plurilingualism: the REFIC (Référentiel de compétences de communication plurilingue en intercompréhension), the REFDIC (Référentiel de formation en intercompréhension (enseignant/formateur)), the FREPA (Framework of Reference for Pluralistic Approaches), these being in turn inspired by the CEFR and its Companion Volume.

Starting from these references, UNITA is integrating their content with a focus on the skills and competences in IC required by each of the actor involved in the IC courses within UNITA - students, teachers, and staff - thus addressing their specific needs.

While IC competences for the formers have already been thoroughly described and analyzed, very little work has been done on the skills of university teachers dealing with plurilingual settings, and almost no researches have touched upon LSP and IC in bureaucratic communication.

General features

As the REFIC states, plurilingualism is both an individual resource and an educational objective which aims at preparing students to actively participate as full citizens in a complex democratic society. A pluralistic linguistic approach is a key approach to develop the linguistic, communicative and cultural repertoire of the individual, also supporting and enhancing the mastery of more languages at the same time.

The three principles of the training process are : I. Consciousness rising, II. Training, III. Improvement

General goals for the development of IC competences are:

- The development of metalinguistic competence and observation skills (ability to rely on the language(s) known to reach other languages, to operate the similarities between the languages of the same family, to resort to the processes of inference);
 - The development of metacognitive competence and the ability to exploit the linguistic repertoire;
- The development of communication strategies and soft skills (eg. the ability to adjust one's own production in first language to an addressee of another language, including in the contexts of Computer Mediated Communication);
- The development of cultural knowledge and intercultural tendency.

COMPREHENSION SKILLS

Learners should develop

- Skimming and scanning strategies
 - o Lexical strategies
 - Lexical correspondences
 - Lexical transparency
 - Semantic field
 - Phonological correspondences
 - Morphological elements
 - o Recognition of keywords and logical connectors
- Inferencing strategies
 - o Making hypothesis based on the context
 - o Using the linguistic repertoire to make connections
- Listening skills

INTERACTION SKILLS

Learners should develop

- Context-based inferences
- Soft skills (intercultural communication)
- Ability to adapt to the situation and modulate / mediate communication (language complexity)
- Ability to detect possible issues in communication
- Remedial and reformulative strategies

At the end of the IC training, participants will have developed the following skills (cfr. REFIC):

- “Communicate orally in multilingual contexts, for example, participate in a dialogue in many languages; use the code-switching and the mix of codes as functional tools as regards the communication and the context;
- Draw in many sources of different languages in order to accomplish tasks of production or interaction in one dominant language;
- Use a linguistic skills’ profile developed unequally in several languages [...];
- Do mediation between languages, for example translate and interpret; explain with simple words in language B the meaning of a reading text in language C;
- Use all the knowledge learned from a former learning process of a language in order to understand texts from languages of the same family (as for UNITA. IC between Romance languages)”.

<https://www.miriadi.net/en/refic>

IC for students

Students will acquire the general principles of IC (as stated above). In particular, they will deal with both oral and written texts, and will perform interproduction tasks in the domains of everyday life and university life. Learners will seek the formal transparencies first on the basis of which activate the processes of interference, using also the contextual indications and their encyclopedic knowledge. The semeiological approach (from the form to the meaning) and the onomasiological approach (from the meaning to the form) are also integrated in a continual back and forth between global comprehension and analysis of the known lexical items.

A third domain of expertise will be the LSP regarding the field of Cultural Heritage, Circular Economy, Renewable Energies. The development of IC skills in these domains will facilitate the communication during students’ mobility, boosting their ability to access specialized content in other languages.

Specific skills to be acquired:

- Autonomy in the learning process
- Metalinguistic awareness of the LSP features (textual genre, lexis, morpho-syntax)
- Interaction in LSP plurilingual contexts

IC for teachers

University teachers will acquire the general principles of IC (as stated above) along with good practices to be applied in their classes where a plurilingual audience is involved.

Specific skills to be acquired:

- Awareness of the importance of the different linguistic repertoires and how to exploit them in the plurilingual class
- Implementation of IC-oriented didactic materials (presentations, notes...)
- LSP communication based in IC principles
 - o Reformulative strategies
 - o Mediation strategies
 - o Use of adequate lexis and morpho-syntax
 - o Scaffolding tools to support the learner
- Use of ICT tools to foster and support plurilingual communication

IC for staff

University staff will acquire the general principles of IC (as stated above) and will focus on the communication in their particular working environment.

Specific skills to be acquired:

- Plurilingual email reading and writing
- IC in managing agreements and international exchanges
- Communication strategies and mediation in administrative context

This deliverable is a first draft based on previous literature and the short experience in the UNITA context. Further and more detailed versions will be implemented in the future and will benefit from the action-research and training that is currently taking place within the alliance.

